

Enforcement of "Phase One Deal" between the U.S. and China: Room for Negotiations

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The "Economic and Trade Agreement between the Government of the United States of America and the Government of the People's Republic of China", known as Phase One Deal, entered into force on February 14, 2020.¹ Through this agreement, China would, among other things, make structural reforms, open its financial services, and strengthen intellectual property. China pledged to buy at least \$200 billion more U.S. goods and services over 2020 and 2021. However, after almost two years, complaints have arisen about China's not meeting its obligations under the Phase One Deal.² According to some statistics, China has reached only sixty two percent of that target.³ As Phase One Deal sets to expire in December 2021, questions arise to its future and compliance and enforcement under the Deal.

The Phase One Deal has come at a time when trade war between the largest economies in the world is still raging. It all began back in 2018 when the U.S. imposed US \$34 billions on imports from China such as aircraft parts.⁴ In return, China imposed 25 percent in tariffs on imports from the U.S. including agricultural products. In the intervening years, the U.S and China exchanged exemptions for certain goods from the imposition of tariffs. However, in recent months, trade war has resumed again as the U.S for instance has extended the ban on U.S. investment in Chinese companies that have ties with the military.⁵

Exemptions from tariff lists and other trade measures of both the U.S. and China seems to work in calming trade relation between them.⁶ This piecemeal approach will likely to continue unless the U.S. and China agree to a new deal, something unlikely to happen. In the alternative, the Phase One Deal can be renewed with tweaking in the numbers involved i.e. how much China would import from the U.S. In this way, the U.S. can rely on hard fought deal and then shifts its focus on enforcement.

According to the Phase One Deal, the U.S. and China agreed to an innovative approach on complying and enforcing their agreement. Chapter seven of the Phase One Deal provides for the steps needed to ensure effective implementation of the agreement. The Phase One Deal created Trade Framework Group to discuss the implementation of agreement, led by the United States Trade Representative and a designated Vice Premier of the People's Republic of China, and a Bilateral Evaluation and Dispute Resolution Office for each Party.⁷ As in a typical trade agreement, a complaining party can submit an appeal to the Bilateral Evaluation and Dispute Resolution Office of the Party Complained Against when there is an issue regarding the agreement. If this issue is not resolved, then the matter can be raised to the designated Deputy United States Trade Representative and the designated Vice Minister.

The Phase One Deal provides that if the concerns of the complaining party are not resolved at the United States Trade Representative and the designated Vice Premier of the People's Republic of China level, then "the Parties shall engage in expedited consultations on the response to the damages or losses incurred by the Complaining

Party".⁸ If the Parties reach consensus on a response, the response shall be implemented. But if the Parties do not reach consensus, the Complaining Party may resort to taking action, including by suspending an obligation under this Agreement or by adopting a remedial measure in a proportionate way that it considers appropriate.⁹

The novelty of the Phase One Deal comes when article 7.4 permits either party, but of course for all practicality it is the U.S., to unilaterally retaliate by suspending an obligation or by adopting a remedial measure in a proportionate way with the purpose of preventing the escalation of the situation and maintaining the normal bilateral trade relationship, as long as the action was taken in good faith. The language used creates room for wide interpretation such as "proportionate way" and "good faith". Rather achieving the purported goals of the Phase One Deal of managing trade in a peaceful manner, the dispute resolution language may lead to escalation of trade tensions between the U.S and China. This is exacerbated by the fact that according to the Phase One Deal, it is the complaining party who makes the determination that there is a violation of the agreement. There is no independent panel or a tribunal that would make that determination. The Phase One Deal is not clear on the remedial measures that can be taken by the complaining party, whether it is the suspension of tariff or quota concessions or imposing additional tariffs and for how long these measures can be taken. In sum, the U.S. can unilaterally determine that a violation has occurred and the duration for suspending concessions and determining the level thereof.

This leaves us with the question if it is expected for both parties, but mainly the U.S., to take unilateral measures to enforce the Phase One Deal. Statements made by U.S. officials indicate that this is likely to happen. However, thus far, evidence shows that enforcement under the Phase One Deal may not happen for several reasons. First, when the U.S. takes an action, China can either accept the remedial measure, along with a promise not to retaliate, or withdraw from Phase One Deal. The latter option is more harmful than taking the remedial measure itself. Second, from economics perspective, whatever targets achieved under the deal is better than nothing or reverting to trade wars with China. Third, from a geopolitical perspective, there are few, if any, alternative venues to force China to abide by its trade obligations. The World Trade Organization (WTO) is in bad shape, especially its Appellate Body "the crown jewel" of the organization responsible for the final say on trade disputes. Even more, there is doubt if the Phase One Deal can be legitimate under WTO rules. The WTO Agreement on Safeguard, provides that "a Member shall not seek, take or maintain any voluntary export restraints, orderly marketing arrangements or any other similar measures on the export or the import side. These include actions taken by a single Member as well as actions under agreements, arrangements and understandings entered into by two or more Members. Any such measure in effect on the date of entry into force of the WTO Agreement shall be brought into conformity with this Agreement or phased out." Clearly, measures such as bilateral voluntary export restraints, orderly marketing agreements, and similar measure that limit imports of certain products are prohibited under WTO rules.

Putting aside the political rhetoric, opening Phase One Deal to re-adjustment and negotiations seems the plausible option in the short term. Phase One Deal has been a success, despite the numbers and flaws in the deal's text. No country should be forced to import from another country. Nevertheless, China was willing to import from the U.S. in increased quantities. In the short term, both the U.S. and China would

continue to exempt on an *ad hoc* basis certain goods and services from harmful tariffs and other trade practices by both countries. Then, the U.S. should give another try for diplomacy and negotiations.

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¹ See Economic and Trade Agreement between the Government of the United States of America and the Government of the People's Republic of China, Jan. 15, 2020, available at <<https://ustr.gov/countries-regions/china-mongolia-taiwan/peoples-republic-china/phase-one-trade-agreement/text>>.

² See Office of the United States Trade Representative, What are they Saying: Ambassador Katherine Tai Outlines the Biden-Harris Administration's New Approach to the U.S.-China Trade Relationship, Oct. 4, 2021, available at <<https://ustr.gov/about-us/policy-offices/press-office/press-releases/2021/october/what-they-are-saying-ambassador-katherine-tai-outlines-biden-harris-administrations-new-approach-us>>.

³ See Chad P. Bown, US-China Phase One Tracker: China's Purchases of US Goods, Nov. 24, 2021, available at <<https://www.piie.com/research/piie-charts/us-china-phase-one-tracker-chinas-purchases-us-goods>>.

⁴ See By David J. Lynch , Danielle Paquette and Emily Rauhala, U.S. Levies Tariffs on \$34 Billion Worth of Chinese Imports, The Washington Post, July 6, 2018, available at <https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/trumps-trade-war-with-china-is-finally-here--and-it-wont-be-pretty/2018/07/05/0e43048c-802c-11e8-b9f0-61b08cdd0ea1_story.html>.

⁵ See New York Times, Biden Expands Trump-Era Ban on Investment in Chinese Firms Linked to Military, June 3, 2021, available at <<https://www.nytimes.com/2021/06/03/us/politics/biden-ban-chinese-firms-trump.html>>.

⁶ See Congressional Research Service, In Focus, Section 301: Tariff Exclusions on U.S. Imports from China, Sep. 9, 2021, available at <<https://sgp.fas.org/crs/row/IF11582.pdf>>

⁷ See Economic and Trade Agreement between the Government of the United States of America and the Government of the People's Republic of China, Chapter 7, art. 7.2, Jan. 15, 2020, available at <https://ustr.gov/sites/default/files/files/agreements/phase%20one%20agreement/Economic_And_Trade_Agreement_Between_The_United_States_And_China_Text.pdf>.

⁸ *Id.* art. 7.4(4)(b).

⁹ *Id.*